

THE IMPACT OF THE INTERNET AND SOCIAL NETWORKS ON THE LIVES OF YOUTH

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Abstract. *The article examines the influence of Internet social networks on modern society. The penetration of social networks into the life of society presupposes their influence on socialization, education of young people, integration into the socio-normative system. Dependence as a concept has three different meanings. The article presents the results of a study of Internet addiction as part of deviant behavior. Therefore, the dysfunction of Internet social networks can be considered as a potential area of deviation, especially in relation to the younger generation.*

Keywords: *internet influence, communication, socialization, modern youth, informational vampirism.*

The development of information technologies is of great importance in modern society. Changes in the structure of society under the influence of the Internet have long been a very interesting topic for researchers. The reason for this is the ambiguous impact of the Internet on people and society, which has both negative and positive consequences. First of all, there is the phenomenon of Internet addiction, which is discussed by domestic and foreign psychologists. Most importantly, Internet addiction is manifested in the fact that people spend a lot of time on the network and forget about their duties and real problems. Unlimited use of computers and the Internet is considered very dangerous for children. Spending a lot of time in front of computer monitors leads to excessive visual activity, which leads to the development of addiction. This is manifested by the appearance of digestive problems, headaches, and difficulties with concentration. It can be noted that we see almost every Internet resource based on the principle of “reading and seeing what is available”. As a result, our attention is more distracted than before, and one of the dangerous consequences of this is the reduction of emotional contact with family and friends in real life, which leads to a number of psychological problems. In our opinion, the Internet also has positive properties. For example, it promotes education, contains valuable materials for raising and training children, there are various websites for parents (online games, online lessons, drawing courses, English, etc.). Many sociologists look at the problem of Internet addiction from the point of view of its impact on the socialization of young people. Through the Internet, all conditions have been created for a person to participate in public activities early. With the help of a computer, one can participate in all spheres of social life. It is worth noting that free access to resources and freedom of speech lead to the creation of a certain kind of culture on the Internet. Users create online communities based on their interests, similar thoughts and worldviews, communication and exchange of information on forums, sites. People who are high-status in real life may not usually be high-status in virtual life, but there are exceptions where low-status users have gradually gained success online. An example is Pavel Durov, the creator of the Telegram social network, which is popular in Russia and abroad.

The Internet has a number of communication functions:

1. Non-verbal communication loses its importance in online communication.

2. Anonymous communication. Due to anonymity, you cannot openly imagine a teenager based on his hidden psychological characteristics, but you can create a different picture that is significantly different from reality.

People who suffer from depression and mental exhaustion or difficulties with social adaptation often use the Internet as a means of entertainment to overcome the difficulties of this interaction.

In conclusion, the Internet plays a very important role in the lives of modern people. To determine the level of influence of the Internet, we present the results of the following survey.

To determine the frequency of Internet use and the most common reasons for visiting websites, young people were diagnosed. The study included 40 respondents aged 20 to 22 years. The study showed that 97.5% of respondents (39 people) use the Internet more than 12 hours a day, and only 2.5% (1 person) use it less than 4 hours a day. The most popular reason for using the Internet is as a means of communication. This option was selected in 38 (40%) out of 95 cases, of which 5 respondents (12.5%) indicated it as the only purpose of visiting the Internet. For only 2 (5%) of the 40 respondents, this purpose turned out to be insignificant, not a priority. The most popular purpose was information search (70% - 28 out of 40), followed by downloading music, movies, books, games, etc.: 20 out of 40 respondents (50%). Online stores are in fourth place (40%) out of 12 respondents. In last (fifth) place, only 40 (4%) out of 10 respondents placed online games. According to the survey, the most visited are social networking sites, forums, chats, etc. The second place is occupied by Internet resources with music, movies and TV shows (60 -24 out of 40%). Finally, in third place are political, humorous sites, sites of various companies and online stores (35% - 14 out of 40). The most popular sites in terms of traffic were social networks, various chats and forums, which confirmed the dominance of the purpose of communication on the Internet. On the other hand, it turned out that respondents who did not set communication as the main goal also often visit sites aimed at this purpose. In fact, there are quite a few people who answer the question "Avoiding getting into a difficult situation by looking for a possible solution or advice?" The most frequently chosen ones are the search engines "Google / Yandex" or forums (100% of respondents).

The answers to this survey show that finding a way out of difficult situations online is more important than advice from loved ones. Summing up the results of this survey, we see that communication among modern youth is mainly carried out online, and we can say how important the Internet is in our lives.

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